

PROBONO

PROBONO ALLIANCE LIAISON (I)

PROBONO - The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods - has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101037075. This output reflects only the author's view, and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Deliverable n°:	D8.5
Deliverable name:	PROBONO Alliance Liaison (I)
Version:	0.9
Release date:	28/12/2022
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Final
Author:	SIN – Salima Ismayilzada

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.5	20/10/2022	ToC	Salima Ismayilzada
0.6	21/10/2022	First Draft version	Salima Ismayilzada
0.7	07.11.2022	Second Draft version	Salima Ismayilzada
0.9	23.12.2022	Final version	Salima Ismayilzada

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
WP8/T8.2
WP8/T8.1

DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Communication Committee
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Secretariat
QM	Quality Management
SC	Scientific Coordinator
TMT	Technical Management Team
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

The PROBONO Alliance- Liaison plan plays a vital role in creating awareness and common knowledge of the PROBONO project. This document presents a plan for event participation/organisation, alliance across projects, and liaison activities of the PROBONO project. These activities will help promote and disseminate the project worldwide.

One of the significant components of the communication and dissemination strategy of the PROBONO project is event participation and/or organisation. Therefore, participation in organising conferences, panels, workshops, etc., will be performed during the project's lifetime by all Consortium members and reported by Communication Committee members using the respective documents.

Besides event participation/organisation, the project also aims to establish synergies and coordination with similar EU projects. In this context, PROBONO will mainly focus on the projects under the Green Deal Projects umbrella to create awareness and interactions with other similar projects.

Last but not least, the plan for internal/external communication activities and an alliance of GBN Innovation Clusters and Advisory Board with the support of WP9 and WP10 will be explained in this document.

1. Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

This section aims to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. D8.5 (PROBONO Alliance Liaison (I)) addresses Task 8.2 (PROBONO Alliance-Liaison and external cooperation), which consists of ST8.2.1 (Liaison activities), ST8.2.2 (Exhibitions and Fairs Presence) and ST8.2.3 (PROBONO communities building Advisory Board & European Alliance of GBN Innovation Clusters). D8.5 will handle the requirements of all these sub-tasks. The primary purpose of T8.2 is to perform networking, alliance across projects, and liaison activities (PROBONO GA, 2022). The goal is to maximise the visibility and impact of the project through partnerships at national, EU, and international levels.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 8.2 PROBONO Alliance-Liaison and external cooperation (M1-M60)	<p>T8.2. PROBONO Alliance-Liaison and external cooperation</p> <p>Perform networking, alliance across projects, and liaison activities. PROBONO will maximise visibility and impact through partnerships at national, EU, and international levels including participation to exhibitions.</p> <p>ST8.2.1 Liaison activities. Ensure the coordination with other H2020/Horizon Europe projects in the EU. This task will create the \ based on the relevant projects including the ones mentioned in Section 2, and initiate discussions to share relevant experiences among similar projects. Connect and invite other projects to the discussion of workshops in other WPs or webinars organised by PROBONO during which project plans can be compared and potential synergies identified. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p> <p>ST8.2.2 Exhibitions and Fairs Presence. Coordinate participation and attend exhibitions and fairs. Exhibitions showcasing various cutting-edge technologies and products related to smart green buildings and neighbourhood would be considered of high importance. Subtask team: [All task partners]</p> <p>ST8.2.3 PROBONO communities building Advisory Board & European Alliance of GBN Innovation Clusters. An alliance of GBN Innovation Clusters and a community building</p>	Chapter 2-4 and Annexes I-IV	The PROBONO Alliance-Liaison and external cooperation plan is described along with the strategy for liaison with other EU projects, event participation, collaboration, and communication with PROBONO AB and Innovation Cluster. The "Monitoring file" together with the "Event list" is also included in Annexes I - II.

	Advisory Board will be formed at the beginning of the project, including other European organisations, associations, and councils with direct relation to the building industry. This will get valuable input for the project in technical, social, environments, legal and economic terms, and to facilitate the dissemination of the project results by extending the PROBONO community. Subtask team: [All task partners]		
DELIVERABLE			
D8.5: PROBONO Alliance Liaison (I) Reports of participation /organisation of events and exhibitions.			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a plan for alliance-liaison activities and external cooperation of the PROBONO project. The report will be based on the T8.2 PROBONO Alliance-Liaison and external cooperation, which contains developing a plan for networking, alliance across projects, and liaison activities.

This document will present the plan for the alliance and liaison activities up to M16. The progress of the task will be presented and reported in D8.6, D8.7, and D8.8 respectively.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPs/Deliverables

This document will first describe liaisons with other EU projects and the way of communication with them in Section 2. Section 3 will explain the strategy for event participation and reporting. This will be followed by Section 4, where the method of the collaboration and communication with PROBONO Advisory Board and GBN Innovation Cluster will be described. Finally, Section 5 will highlight the conclusions and the plans of action to be implemented in the following months.

As explained above, Task 8.2 is a component of WP8 and has mutual interdependence with T8.1 (Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities) since event participation and alliance-liaison activities are also a part of the communication and dissemination strategy.

Furthermore, WP10, as a leading work package for the Advisory Board and WP9, as a creator for GBN Innovation Clusters, will actively participate in T8.2 progress. The outcomes of LLs (WP7), D7.8; D7.11; D7.14; D7.17; D7.20; D7.23, and WP5 on the topic of DT and LCA will also be the main fertiliser for liaison with other EU projects.

2 Liaisons with other EU Projects and Programme Meetings

The PROBONO project aims to establish synergies and coordination with similar EU projects. The project will mainly focus on the projects under the Green Deal Projects umbrella with the purpose of creating awareness and interactions with other similar projects for policy, market, and technology-relevant issues.

European Commission "Green Deal Projects" has been identified as the most relevant initiative for PROBONO activities at the beginning of the project. It is an EU funded initiative which has the objective of uniting Horizon 2020 Projects from several fields to identify and tackle the barriers which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation. One main characteristic of this initiative is that it is structured into well-defined working groups developing on different topics related to cross-cutting issues. The PROBONO project is a part of the Urban Environment and Mobility working group together with the following EU projects (See Table2). The goal is to establish synergies and collaboration with these projects during the project's lifetime.

PROBONO has participated in two "Green Deal Projects" meetings where the plan for future collaboration has been discussed. In the first meeting, the initiative's main goal was introduced, and the working groups were identified. The second meeting was dedicated to the presentations of the projects and discussion of the current challenges and barriers. The next meeting will happen in the summer, where the collaboration among respective projects will be planned and established.

Acronym	Short Description
NetZeroCities	NetZeroCities (NZC) is part of the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme in support of European Union's Green Deal. NZC has been designed to help cities overcome the current structural, institutional and cultural barriers they face in order to achieve climate neutrality by 2030.
PIONEERS	PIONEERS aims to reduce the number of Powered Two-Wheeler fatalities and severely injured by increasing the safety,

	performance, comfort and usage rate of Personal Protective Equipment and the development of new on-board safety devices.
MAGPIE	MAGPIE's ambition is to force a breakthrough in the supply and use of green energy carriers in transport to, from and within ports. We will create energy efficiencies and support developments that make green-energy carriers available to users. By demonstrating and implementing smart solutions in the realm of digitalization and automation, we will facilitate and contribute to the decarbonization of port-related transport.
OLGA	The OLGA project aims to demonstrate the impact of the environmental innovations and concepts presented at the lighthouse airport and occasionally directly in fellow airports. Such innovations are scalable and generic, laying the foundations for greener airports throughout Europe. Therefore, the project will replicate several innovation activities from the lighthouse airport at fellow airports: Milano Malpensa in Italy, Zagreb in Croatia, and Cluj Napoca in Romania.
TULIPS	TULIPS is a consortium that will develop innovations that facilitate the transition to low-carbon mobility and enhance sustainability at airports for the next four years, supported by the EU with €25 million in funding.
STARGATE	STARGATE will identify the vulnerabilities of current farming systems, landscape management, models, methods and practices related to climate change and

	conduct a thorough requirements' analysis for the Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) on the basis of which it will shape the stakeholder community.
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Table 2: Liaisons with other EU initiatives

Moreover, there are two sister projects (See Table3) that are funded under the same topic of PROBONO and collaborations with these projects are expected during the coming years. There has been a kick-off meeting with the sister projects where the plan for the collaboration has been discussed. According to this initial plan, the projects will contribute to one another's websites, social media channels and newsletters. There will be annual meetings with the sister projects to discuss the progress and improvement of the established plan. The next meeting will be held in 2023.

Acronym	Short Description
oPEN Lab	oPEN Lab is an EU-funded project leading the transition to Positive Energy Neighbourhoods (PENs) in Tartu (Estonia), Pamplona (Spain) and Genk (Belgium).
ARV	ARV is a H2020 EU-funded project aiming at creating climate positive circular communities in Europe and increasing the building renovation rate on the continent.

Table 3: Liaisons with H2020 sister projects

Furthermore, the interaction with other projects, besides Green Deal projects, will also be considered if there is an opportunity. The main focus on this topic will be the other EU projects.

3 Events

One of the complementary means of dissemination is event participation and/or organisation. Therefore, participation in conferences, panels, workshops, roundtables, etc., will be performed during the project's lifetime. These activities will help:

- Maintain and strengthen the commitment level of the target audience.
- Share the project progress and results.
- Increase visibility of the project through presentations, publications, interviews, debates, panels, etc.
- Establish new collaborations and maintaining interaction with existing allies

Regarding the event participation, "Monitoring file" (See ANNEX 1) will be used for tracking of the participation in events for each partner. The "Event List" file (ANNEX II) presents a list of relevant events that will be held this year or in upcoming years with additions from partners through the Communication Committee. This is not a definitive list since event dates and details might change in the future.

The "Event" list should continuously be updated on the partners' suggestions and the European Union's event calendar. Partners should actively contribute to identifying relevant external events outside of participating in events. Moreover, each Communication Committee member oversees updating the list of the local events. The partner will decide on the events they want to participate in if they are using their own budget. If the usage of the WP8 budget is required, the WP8 leader will make the last decision regarding the event participation. Event selection and participation process will be discussed in monthly Communication Committee meetings if needed. The list is available in the PROBONO internal repository. The WP8 leader will keep track of it, and a notification regarding the update should be sent to the WP8 leader.

When participating in events, the partners can ask for additional communication materials to those available, targeted towards a specific event (brochures, flyers, infographics, video presentations, etc.) two weeks before the event. This request should be sent to the WP8 leader. More detailed information regarding the communication materials can be found in D8.1.

4 Advisory Board and European Alliance of GBN Innovation Clusters

4.1 Advisory Board

The Advisory Board will offer impartial scientific advice, support the PST, and advise the consortium on social, environmental, technological, legal, and economic factors that may influence the innovation management of PROBONO. It will be chaired by one of its members (See Annex III), elected upon the AB's first meeting in M1 (PROBONO GA,2022). The collaboration and communication between AB and the PROBONO project will be implemented by WP10 and WP8 leaders via annual meetings and monthly newsletters. The first meeting between the PROBONO Advisory Board and the WP8 leader will be held in the first week of January 2023. The progress of the project, communication and dissemination activities, the plan for the next year, and the alliance strategy with AB will be discussed in this meeting.

4.2 GBN Innovation Clusters

GBNs are still conceptual, as reflected in deliverable D1.10 from the PROBONO project. Thus, the concept of the GBN Innovation Cluster will be refined based on PROBONO's achievements and outputs. However, considering the main conclusions of T1.5, each GBN Innovation Cluster refers to the main stakeholders within any neighbourhood responsible for developing, implementing and managing aspects that impact upon the daily lives of citizens and communities in terms of quality of life, well-being, sustainability and resilience, including also those profiles that are required to ensure that the GBN condition is achieved: the facilitator and the mediator (see all details in the already mentioned D1.10).

The GBN Innovation Cluster at a local level will facilitate a common understanding on the needs and expectations. Thus, they will be responsible for the community building and translating to the local preferences (considering the political, environmental, socioeconomic, legal, or cultural context) towards each GBN objectives.

For the sake of maximising the project results, the European Alliance of GBN Innovation Clusters will help upscale and replicate the results at the local, regional, and national levels. GBN Innovation Clusters will be established during the project as the natural process of setting up the project LLs, with strong cooperation between WP1, WP2, WP8 and WP9. Moreover, this is

considered a key concept that is expected to be exploited and replicated beyond PROBONO (as reflected in the project KPIs defined within WP6) as reflected by the exploitation plan that will be delivered as D9.2.

5 Conclusion

The goal of the PROBONO Alliance- Liaison plan is to disseminate the projects and engage project partners, stakeholders, and end-users through event participation/organisation, liaison activities with other EU projects, and alliance across projects. Event participation/organisation activities have already been started by various Consortium members. At the same time, the Dissemination Leader of the project, together with the Project Coordinator and Technical Coordinator, has already participated in Green Deal Projects meetings and established collaboration with sister projects.

References

PROBONO GA. (2022). *The PROBONO project, Grant Agreement.*

ANNEX III

1	World Green Building Council
2	German Sustainable Building Council
3	American International Group UK Limited & AIG Europe S. A
4	Asociacion Madrid Subterra PTE-ee
5	Ecochange Srls
6	Facilities First Australia
7	Asociación de Empresas de Redes de Calor y Frío

*Table 4: Advisory Board Members***ANNEX IV**

Target description		Target Goal
Events	N° of participants in the final project conference	200
	N° of international conferences as speaker	6
	N° of presentations in conferences	10
Workshops & Roundtables	N° of workshops as co-organizer	4

Table 5: KPI List